

Synthesis, characterization and biological properties of binuclear complexes of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} with 3,4-diphenyl-5-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-1,2,5-triazapenta-2,4-diene (DHTP)

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Abstract : The synthesis and characterization of a series of homo binuclear metal complexes of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} with the titled ligand 3,4-diphenyl-5-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-1,2,5-triazapenta-2,4-diene (DHTP) have been reported. The complexes have been synthesized by treating an ethanolic solution of the ligand with equimolar amount of appropriate metal salts in ethanol by a direct route and also by template synthesis using *in situ* method. The ligand and its metal complexes have been characterized on the basis of analytical and spectral data, thermal analysis, magnetic and conductivity measurements. Based on the results, tentative structures of the complexes have been proposed. The ligand as well as the metal complexes exhibit antimicrobial activities against the pathogenic fungus *Aspergillus niger*, *Helminthosporium oryzae* and *Fusarium oxysporium*. The fungicidal activities of the complexes have been compared with a standard fungicide Fluconazole.

Keywords : Macrocyclic complex, thermal analysis, antimicrobial activity, conductivity measurements, Fluconazole.

Introduction

Schiff base complexes continue to remain an important and popular area of research due to their simple synthesis, versatility and diverse range of applications¹⁻⁴ in organic synthesis and metal ion complexation⁵. The studies on homobimetallic complexes in which two metal centers are held in closed proximity have addressed their ligand environment, redox behavior, magnetic exchange interactions, spectroscopic properties and more over they exhibit distinct reactivity pattern as compared to the corresponding monometallic complexes⁶. Therefore these types of complexes persistently play a very significant role in understanding the various aspects of coordination chemistry of metals⁷.

In view of the above facts, in the present communication, we report the synthesis and characterization of some new homo and bimetallic metal complexes from the reaction of benzilmonohydrazone and *o*-aminophenol in presence of metal ions like Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Co²⁺.

Benzilmonohydrazone⁸ was chosen as the model starting material and it was envisaged that the carbonyl func-

tion could be condensed with amine groups and a new series of complexes containing the open chain ligands could be derived from it. *In situ* condensation of benzilmonohydrazone in presence of metal ions like Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} with *o*-aminophenol is also expected to give rise to same desired complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvents used are either of Glaxo or Merck grade. The solvents were purified before use in the reaction. The metal contents i.e. copper and nickel in all the complexes were estimated by standard gravimetric methods⁹, while that of cobalt was carried out by reported method¹⁰. The percentage of nitrogen was calculated by combustion method. The values obtained were also supported by semi micro Kjeldahl's method. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated with CHN microanalyser. The IR spectra of the metal complexes were recorded on a Varian spectrophotometer, Australia, in KBr pellets in the region 4000-400 cm⁻¹. The electronic spectra of the complexes in DMSO were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-398 spectrophotometer. The conductivity of the complexes in DMF

was measured with a Philips conductivity bridge (Model CLO-06, cell constant 0.5 cm^{-1}) using $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ solution of the complex in DMF. The room temperature magnetic moment values have been determined by Gouy method with mercury tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II), $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant. The electron spin resonance spectra were recorded as powder sample (polycrystalline) on an E-112 EPR spectrophotometer with field set at 3200G, scan range $2.0 \times 1 \text{ kg}$, modulation frequency 100 KHz, microwave frequency 9.4 GHz, receiver gain 10×10^2 and modulation amplitude $0.63 \times 10\text{G}$. The thermogravimetric analysis was carried out in a DTA/TG instrument STA 409C in nitrogen atmosphere.

Synthesis of the ligand and its metal complexes :

The synthesis of the ligand and the complexes of the present investigation were made following the literature method^{11,12}, as given below.

Preparation of the Schiff base (DHTP) from benzilmonohydrazone and ortho aminophenol :

In the first step, in a 100 ml short necked round bottomed flask, benzil (20.8 g) was taken in ethanol (50 ml) and to this was added hydrazine hydrate 80% (12.5 ml) and heated under reflux for 2 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, when a white crystalline product of benzilmonohydrazone (BMH) was separated and then it was recrystallized from ethanol and dried over fused CaCl_2 . Melting point $152 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (lit. m.p. $150\text{--}152 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

In the second step, in a 100 ml short necked round bottomed flask 5.6 g of benzilmonohydrazone (BHM) was taken in 50 ml of ethanol (90% alcohol) and to this *o*-aminophenol (2.25 g) in 1 : 1 molar ratio was added followed by 2 to 3 drops of glacial acetic acid and was heated under reflux for 3–4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled when the Schiff base was precipitated. It was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol when the desired product was obtained (Melting point is $143 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

Preparation of binuclear metal(II) complexes :

The binuclear metal(II) complexes of the Schiff base were prepared in two different methods. In one of the methods, the ligand was separated and interacted with metal ions in appropriate stoichiometry (1 : 1) yielding the complexes. In the other, the complexes were prepared by *in situ* template reaction of benzilmonohydrazone with *o*-aminophenol in the presence of the metal ions. How-

ever, in both the cases complexes of the same stoichiometry were isolated. In the present communication we report the synthesis and characterization of the complexes obtained from *in situ* reaction.

Synthesis of DHTP copper(II) chloride :

0.448 g of benzilmonohydrazone (2 mmol) was taken in a 100 ml short necked round bottom flask and was dissolved in 30 ml of ethanol followed by addition of 0.340 g $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2 mmol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h. It was then cooled to room temperature and 0.218 g of *o*-aminophenol (2 mmol) in ethanol was added dropwise and then refluxed for 2 h, when an orange yellow precipitate was obtained on cooling. It was filtered and washed several times with ethanol and finally dried over fused calcium chloride in a desiccator.

The bromo and nitrate complexes were prepared in a similar manner. The same *in situ* reaction method was also adopted for other metal complexes. The analytical and molar conductance data of the binuclear metal complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and discussion

The amino and carbonyl functions in benzilmonohydrazone exist in *trans* configuration with respect to C–C bond. In the presence of a metal ion, it attains a *cis* configuration thereby bringing the $-\text{NH}_2$ and the carbonyl function to close proximity, that facilitates the condensation of benzilmonohydrazone with *o*-aminophenol giving rise to the corresponding metal complex. The scheme of the reaction is presented in Fig. 1.

The complexes are highly coloured and have melting point greater than $250 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. They are insoluble in most of the organic solvents but are soluble in *N,N'*-dimethylformamide (DMF).

The molar conductance of binuclear Schiff base complexes were recorded in DMF (10^{-3} M) at room temperature. The complexes showed high molar conductance values ($135\text{--}145 \text{ } \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) which indicate that the complexes are electrolytic in nature with the anions outside the coordination sphere.

Infrared spectra :

The IR spectra provide a wealth of information on the structure and bonding in the complexes. The spectra of all the complexes exhibit almost similar pattern in the finger

Table 1. Analytical and conductance data of binuclear complexes of DHTP

Complexes	Colour	Mol. wt.	% Found (Calcd.)					Cl/Br	Λ ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
			M	C	H	N ^a			
[Cu(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	Orange yellow	898	13.93 (14.14)	53.40 (53.45)	4.36 (4.45)	9.11 (9.35)	7.41 (7.90)	135	
[Cu(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Br ₂	Dark brown	987	12.91 (12.87)	47.59 (48.63)	3.98 (4.05)	7.98 (8.51)	15.89 (16.21)	136	
[Cu(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Green	951	13.01 (13.35)	49.67 (50.47)	3.97 (4.21)	11.01 (11.78)	-	136	
[Ni(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	Grey	888	12.98 (13.22)	53.67 (54.05)	4.01 (4.50)	8.78 (9.45)	7.93 (8.00)	138	
[Ni(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Br ₂	Silver grey	977	11.79 (12.02)	48.27 (49.13)	3.96 (4.09)	7.98 (8.60)	15.78 (16.38)	139	
[Ni(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Dark green	941	12.08 (12.48)	50.95 (51.01)	4.12 (4.25)	11.04 (11.90)	-	139	
[Co(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	Brown	889	13.03 (13.25)	52.56 (53.99)	4.05 (4.50)	9.12 (9.45)	6.87 (7.99)	142	
[Co(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Br ₂	Grey	978	11.79 (12.05)	48.46 (49.08)	3.91 (4.09)	8.13 (8.59)	15.93 (16.36)	143	
[Co(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Marine green	942	11.86 (12.51)	49.38 (50.96)	4.01 (4.25)	11.23 (11.89)	-	145	

^aIncluding nitrate nitrogen.

Fig. 1. Scheme of reaction.

print region, suggesting them to be isostructural. The IR spectra of the complexes are compared with similar type of other complexes.

The spectra of the complexes are found to be little complicated. However, attempts have been made to identify certain bands, which provide valuable information as

regards to the elucidation of the structure of the complexes¹³. The Schiff base condensation is evidenced by the disappearance of $\nu_{C=O}$ due to benzilmonohydrazone and appearance of $\nu_{C=N}$ (azomethine group)¹⁴ in the vicinity of $1590\text{--}1595\text{ cm}^{-1}$. A broad band splitting into two bands in the region $3450\text{--}3321\text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been presumed to be due to the combined mode of ν_{O-H} of coordinated water and ν_{N-H} of primary amine. The band due to ν_{N-H} appears in the region $3050\text{--}3020\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The broadness of the band may be ascribed to inter/intramolecular hydrogen bonding. The participation of water in coordination is supported¹⁵ by the appearance of a band at 1023 cm^{-1} due to δ_{H_2O} and ν_{M-O} ¹⁶ at around $680\text{--}685\text{ cm}^{-1}$, other bands due to ν_{C-O} and ν_{N-N} are also observed in the region $1410\text{--}1420\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1100\text{--}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. In the lower frequency region bands around 478 cm^{-1} assignable to ν_{M-N} are observed¹⁷. The above IR spectral evidences reveal that the coordination framework of the ligand involves azomethine nitrogen of hydrazone moiety, imine function and phenolic oxygen of *o*-aminophenol and the two *trans* axial sites are filled up by coordinated water molecules.

Thermal analysis :

Since IR spectra of the complexes indicate the presence of coordinated water, thermogravimetric analysis was carried out to ascertain their nature. The thermogram of the chloride complex of copper(II) is recorded in Fig. 2. This shows that the complex undergoes two step decomposition processes. The first step is observed at around $\sim 200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with an endothermic peak at $\sim 210\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

The weight loss is due to the loss of four molecules of water.

Their elimination ($>100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) indicates the involvement of water molecules in coordination¹⁸ and their removal at the same temperature range is suggestive of their similar chemical environment in the complex.

The second step of decomposition observed at around $390\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ indicates the decomposition of the organic components in the complex leaving behind copper oxide as the final product. The decomposition process is endothermic which is in conformity with system undergoing bond breaking in thermal process. The same thermal behaviour is exhibited by Ni-Ni as well as Co-Co systems. The thermal stability of the complexes are found to be in the order of $\text{Cu-Cu} > \text{Co-Co} > \text{Ni-Ni}$.

The thermo analytical data of the binuclear metal complexes of DHTP are given in Table 2.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of the complexes $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHTP})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2\text{X}_2$ display a broad band at 22727 cm^{-1} (440 nm) indicating Cu^{II} centre to be in an approximately distorted octahedral environment. However, instead of getting three bands due to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow 2A_{1g}(\nu_1)$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow 2B_{2g}(\nu_2)$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow 2E_g(\nu_3)$ for d^9 system, only one broad band is observed suggesting that all the ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 bands are superimposed due to small energy difference into a single broad band which is analogous to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow 2T_{2g}$ transition. The width and asymmetry of the band provides evidence for Jahn-Teller distortion.

Fig. 2. Thermogram of the complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHTP})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2\text{Cl}_2$.

Table 2. Thermo analytical data of binuclear metal complexes

Complexes	Temperature range of decomposition (°C)	% of Wt. loss Found (Calcd.)	Remarks
[Cu(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	200	7.89 (8.02)	Loss of four water molecules
	390	17.57 (17.71)	Formation of metal oxides
[Co(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	190	7.92 (8.10)	Loss of four water molecules
	370	16.73 (16.86)	Formation of metal oxides
[Ni(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	180	7.83 (8.11)	Loss of four water molecules
	360	16.67 (16.82)	Formation of metal oxides

Further non occurrence of bands below 10000 cm⁻¹ (1000 nm) rules out the possibility of tetrahedral or pseudo tetrahedral geometry for the Cu^{II} centre. The observed magnetic moment values of the complexes lie in the range of 1.79–1.84 B.M. which is commensurate with spin free two hexa coordinated Cu^{II} centre.

The electronic spectral studies of the complexes [Ni(DHTP)(H₂O)₂]₂X₂ exhibit two bands at 12948 cm⁻¹ (772 nm) and 20660 cm⁻¹ (484 nm) which has been assigned to ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(P) transitions respectively in an approximately octahedral field¹⁹. The more intense band at higher frequency region near 25380 cm⁻¹ (394 nm) is believed to arise due to charge transfer (CT) transition. All the complexes are found to be paramagnetic. The magnetic moment of all the complexes lie in the range of 2.79–2.86 B.M. which is the expected value for octahedral Ni^{II} complexes.

In the complexes [Co(DHTP)(H₂O)₂]₂X₂ three bands are observed in the region ~ 11100 cm⁻¹ (900 nm), 13790 cm⁻¹ (725 nm) and 17400 cm⁻¹ (574 nm). The first band may be assigned to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F), second band to be ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g} and the third band is due to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(P) transitions respectively in an approximately octahedral field around cobalt(II) centres²⁰. The high frequency band at 26700 cm⁻¹ (375 nm) has been assigned to charge transfer (CT) transition. The magnetic moment values of the complexes lie in the range of 4.72–4.81 B.M. The

magnetic moment in all the complexes is at higher value than the normal range. This is due to high spin octahedral structure for the complexes. The position of the electronic absorption bands indicate the presence of octahedral environment around Co^{II} ion in all the complexes, which is supported by magnetic moment values. The electronic spectra and magnetic properties of complexes are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Electronic spectra and magnetic properties of complexes

Complexes	Band position (cm ⁻¹)	Assignment	μ _{eff} (B.M.)
[Cu(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	22727	² E _g → ² T _{2g}	1.81
	26900	CT	
[Cu(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Br ₂	19438	² E _g → ² T _{2g}	1.79
	26000	CT	
[Cu(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	20050	² E _g → ² T _{2g}	1.84
	27350	CT	
[Ni(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	12948	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (F)	2.79
	20660	³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{1g} (P)	
	25380	CT	
[Ni(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Br ₂	12048	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (F)	2.91
	20408	³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{1g} (P)	
	25640	CT	
[Ni(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	11940	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (F)	2.86
	19047	³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{1g} (P)	
	25760	CT	
[Co(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	11100	⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (F)	4.72
	13790	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ A _{2g}	
	17400	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)	
	26700	CT	
[Co(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ Br ₂	11700	⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (F)	4.78
	14190	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ A _{2g}	
	16800	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)	
	26300	CT	
[Co(DHTP)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	12200	⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (F)	4.81
	14900	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ A _{2g}	
	17540	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)	
	26500	CT	

The electronic spectra of the complexes are given in Fig. 3.

Electron spin resonance :

The ESR spectrum of binuclear Schiff base Cu^{II} complex exhibits two signals at g_⊥, g_∥ and g_{av} = (g_⊥ + 2g_∥)/3 = 2.211. These values indicate the presence of un-

Fig. 3. Electronic spectra of the complexes : (a) = $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHTP})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2\text{Cl}_2$, (b) = $[\text{Ni}(\text{DHTP})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2\text{Cl}_2$, (c) = $[\text{Co}(\text{DHTP})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2\text{Cl}_2$.

paired electron in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital giving octahedral geometry²¹.

In the axial spectra, the g -values are related with exchange interaction coupling constant (G) by the expression $G = (g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)$. The values of G reflect the spin interaction between Cu^{II} centres of the binuclear Cu^{II} complex. According to Hathaway and Billing²² if $G > 4$, the spin exchange interaction is negligible and if $G < 4$ considerable spin-exchange interaction prevails. In our present investigation, G value comes out to be 4.96 which suggest negligible spin exchange interaction between the two copper ions which is the evidence for monomeric nature of the complex²³.

These data are in agreement with those obtained from the electronic spectra which confirm the octahedral geometry for Cu^{II} Schiff base complexes. The ESR spectral data of binuclear Cu^{II} complex is given in Table 4.

Table 4. ESR spectral data of binuclear Cu^{II} complex					
Complex	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	Δg	G
$[\text{Cu}(\text{DHTP})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2\text{Cl}_2$	2.452	2.091	2.211	0.360	4.96

The ESR spectrum of binuclear Cu^{II} complex is given in Fig. 4.

Based on the above physico-chemical evidences the following structure has been proposed (Fig. 5) for the metal complexes.

Fungicidal activities :

The ligand DHTP and its homo binuclear metal com-

Fig. 4. ESR spectra of the complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{DHTP})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2\text{Cl}_2$.

Where $M = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ and $X = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{NO}_3^-$

Fig. 5. Structure of the metal complexes.

plexes with $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ and Co^{II} were screened for antifungal activity²⁴ against *Aspergillus niger*, *Helminthosporium oryzae* and *Fusarium oxysporium*. It is known that chelation tends to make the ligand to act as more powerful and potent antifungal agent. This may be due to inhibition of enzyme production as a result of chelation of the ligand through N and O donor system with metal ion. Chelation also reduces the polarity of the central metal ion because of partial sharing of its +ve charge with the donor group and possible π electron delocalization within the whole chelate ring. This increases the nature of central metal ion which favours its permeation through lipid layers of the cell membrane²⁵⁻²⁷. This increased lipophilicity enhances the penetration of complexes into the lipid membrane and blocks the metal binding sites in enzymes of microorganisms. These $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ and Co^{II} complexes also disturb the respiration process and thus block the synthesis of proteins, which restrict further growth of the organisms.

Table 5. Antifungal screening data of metal complexes of (DHTP)
 Values are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. (n=3)

Complexes	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>				<i>Helminthosporium oryzae</i>				<i>Fusarium oxysporium</i>										
	25	50	100		25	50	100		25	50	100								
DHTP	7.16 \pm 0.33	9.0 \pm 0.289	10.83 \pm 0.411	8.33 \pm 0.167	10.167 \pm 0.167	12.167 \pm 0.441	11.833 \pm 0.33	13.167 \pm 0.167	15.833 \pm 0.167	14.632 \pm 0.129	16.354 \pm 0.239	20.012 \pm 0.127	15.187 \pm 0.254	17.567 \pm 0.258	23.341 \pm 0.156	17.645 \pm 0.267	25.392 \pm 0.257	27.512 \pm 0.231	
Fluconazole	8.5 \pm 0.289	11.4 \pm 0.208	15.03 \pm 0.297	10.3 \pm 0.265	12.967 \pm 0.328	15.633 \pm 0.176	14.033 \pm 0.441	18.867 \pm 0.203	21.067 \pm 0.536	10.767 \pm 0.536	13.0 \pm 0.361	15.33 \pm 0.167	12.8 \pm 0.208	14.1 \pm 0.346	16.6 \pm 0.058	14.367 \pm 0.219	19.33 \pm 0.186	19.633 \pm 0.291	
(H ₂ O) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	11.60 \pm 0.100	12.667 \pm 0.088	16.7 \pm 0.115	14.067 \pm 0.285	14.467 \pm 0.285	18.733 \pm 0.328	15.167 \pm 0.203	20.567 \pm 0.291	24.467 \pm 0.145	10.933 \pm 0.296	13.133 \pm 0.233	16.433 \pm 0.120	11.767 \pm 0.176	13.733 \pm 0.273	16.367 \pm 0.133	14.600 \pm 0.208	20.933 \pm 0.219	23.367 \pm 0.120	
[Ni(DHTP)]	11.100 \pm 0.306	14.433 \pm 0.120	16.900 \pm 0.208	13.400 \pm 0.100	15.700 \pm 0.321	19.500 \pm 0.115	16.767 \pm 0.219	22.50 \pm 0.208	23.767 \pm 0.176	12.533 \pm 0.203	16.133 \pm 0.120	19.433 \pm 0.176	14.333 \pm 0.088	15.467 \pm 0.145	18.400 \pm 0.153	23.400 \pm 0.153	26.433 \pm 0.230		
(H ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂	10.833 \pm 0.176	13.433 \pm 0.145	16.467 \pm 0.203	12.400 \pm 0.058	14.433 \pm 0.167	18.567 \pm 0.291	15.5 \pm 0.153	23.400 \pm 0.058	24.667 \pm 0.088	13.533 \pm 0.088	15.533 \pm 0.176	18.767 \pm 0.176	14.467 \pm 0.088	16.433 \pm 0.120	21.533 \pm 0.088	16.333 \pm 0.088	24.600 \pm 0.153	25.367 \pm 0.145	
[Cu(DHTP)]	15.533 \pm 0.033	17.533 \pm 0.088	21.633 \pm 0.088	15.500 \pm 0.115	18.5 \pm 0.058	23.6 \pm 0.153	19.400 \pm 0.153	27.533 \pm 0.176	28.533 \pm 0.088										

The antifungal activities of the complexes were tested by the method of Horsfall²⁸. The evaluation was carried out at different concentrations (ppm) in dioxane. The amount of germination or growth inhibition was determined after inoculation of the fungal spores into Czapek Dox agar-agar media. Spores were also inoculated onto the agar-agar media containing the test sample. The whole system was kept in an incubator for five days. The percentage of inhibition was calculated as follows :

$$\% \text{ of inhibition} = 100(P - Q)/p$$

where P = area of colony growth without test sample and Q = area of the colony growth with the test sample.

The copper(II) complexes are found to be more active than the other binuclear complexes and the ligand DHTP. When compared with the fungicidal activity of a known drug²⁹, Fluconazole, it has been observed that though its efficiency is greater than that of the free ligand DHTP and its Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes, the Cu^{II} complex with DHTP, however, has a very close fungicidal activity as that of Fluconazole itself (Table 5). The activity order is found to be Fluconazole \geq Cu₂ > Co₂ > Ni₂ > DHTP and with respect to anion, the binuclear complexes follow the order Br⁻ > Cl⁻ > NO₃⁻. The statistical calculations adopting two ways ANOVA test³⁰ have also indicated significant difference with respect to different treatment of complexes (Table 5).

The fungicidal activities of the drug Fluconazole, binuclear metal complexes and the ligand (DHTP) are presented in the following bar diagram (Fig. 6) taking the chloride complexes at concentration level of 100 ppm.

Fig. 6. Fungicidal activities of the complexes of DHTP.

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